

Conceptualizing Career Development Model for Arab Nations: Jordanian Students' Perspectives

Author's Details:

Mohammad Saleh Salem Alkaraki¹ Prof. (Dr) Salleh Abd Rashid²

^{1,2}School of Human Development and Technocommunication, Universiti Malaysia Perlis

Abstract

The existing literatures on teenage and adolescent decision making have done a lot in terms of assessing career choice factors in many contexts. There are studies on different racial groups, different age groups, different gender, and even different races. There are also studies for people from different nationalities and different family contexts. However, studies are lacking from the perspectives of developing Nations particularly the Middle Eastern Countries including Jordan. Factors used in other countries particularly the Western Nations are to be applied on Jordan students to ascertain the extent of generalization of these studies. This study, thus proposed family role, community influences and cultural factors as likely determinants of Jordanian students career choice. The study is a conceptual work with the aim to propose the variables based on literatures. It is part of a PhD thesis on this field of study which will be empirically validated in no distance time. Academics will be updated accordingly through publications after validation of the model. This study will contribute to knowledge through integration and application of variables hitherto used in developed Nations on developing Nations. Jordanian students will benefit from this study as a guide to their present and future choices.

Keywords: Career choice, family role, community influence, cultural factors, Arab Nations.

1.0 Introduction

Career developing is a critical social phenomenon every adult pass through in life (Savickas, 2008; Gunz & Peiper, 2007; Wiseman, et al., 2010; Kulkami, 2012; Kunnen, 2013). Most challenging is how to make choice among competing alternatives. Social psychologist viewed career choices in the same manner with "career developments" or "occupational interests and aspiration" (Teng et al., 1999). Career choice is simply defined as long life process of engaging the work world through choosing among employment opportunities made available to job seekers (Bandura et al. 2001; Ferry, 2006). Choosing a career may not be as simple as defined, because choice of career is quite important decision in life due to its aftermath effects on other things; it affects the continuity of the study, the successes and/or failure of the person concerned, and satisfaction or dissatisfaction. Therefore, career choice is a significant life decision that involves consideration of many factors including environmental, social, economic, cultural and even religion. This perception will be address from both advanced and emerging Nations to crossbreed influential variables within and across Nations.

2.0 Global Perception of Career Choice

In many parts of the world, a lot of people have placed emphasis on career choice as an important aspect of their life decision. However, this could be as a result of the norms that surround career issues in some part of the globe (Johnson & Mortimer, 2002). For example Asian-Americans are known to pursue careers that both meet their own self-interests as well as acceptable to their parents (Leone & Chou, 1994; US bureau of the census 1992) as opposed to white Americans who tend to pursue career options that are driven by their self-drive or self-actualisation influenced by their desire to be independent of their parents (Teng et al., 1999; US bureau of the census, 1992). In the Middle East however, the determination of a person's social and cultural status is the most favoured consideration. This is because of the correlation that existed between the nature of job and people's perception about the holder of that job or career.

Good choice of career is a key determinant of the extent to which a person attains his/her life goals (Soenens & Vansteenkiste, 2005). These goals could both be during one's education or after the completion of schooling programs. Accordingly, the perception of Western world on career choice is often accompanied by a

consideration of the concerned person's abilities and core competencies in the career area chosen. This ensures that the person chooses a career in which one has the best abilities and core competencies (Kerka, 2000; Buser, Niedexle & Oosterbeck, 2014). According to Buser et al., (2014) abilities and core competencies will best determine a candidates' subject competitiveness. That competitiveness is strongly and positively linked to academic ability and subject performance. Most importantly, Buser et al., (2014) also found that core competences and abilities make crucial differences between girls and boys in choosing their subjects.

However, this is not always the case especially in the developing world, choosing a career in an area of one's core competencies and greatest abilities has been determined to greatly enhance the career prospects of the person concerned (Cenkseven-Onder, Kirdok & Isik, 2010). Among other things, being highly competent and skilled in a given career area ensures that the chances of the person succeeding in that area are higher. Furthermore, such a person is more likely to enjoy the career more if he/she is gifted and competent in the career area than if reverse is the case (Kerka, 2000). This view is also strengthened by the study conducted by Da Silva et al. (2010) that personal values and prestige associated with the job are important factors. In a related development, passion for the job is another strong factor that ensures successful career development. In many instances, passion for/or something has been determined to be a major contributor to success in the area than even the greatest abilities and competencies in the area (Cenkseven-Onder, Kirdok & Isik, 2010; Kulkami, 2012). The crux of the matter is that one cannot successfully pursue a career in an area in which one has not deep-rooted interest. Apart from interest and competency, cultural differences also shape career perception from global perspectives.

For example, the generally believe is that people of Chinese origin (of which the Taiwanese and the Hong Kong people are part) are easily influenced by the need to fit in and to be socially acceptable. In essence, the decision-making processes of people of Chinese origin, whether it is about career or any other issue in life, is greatly influenced by public perceptions and the need to be accepted. These decisions include even on issues such as the dress code and the school to attend (Haase, 2011).

Globalization has intensified competition at job market, the movement of people and knowledge across countries is at the increase. The implication of this is that, people with little flexibility will be dominated by expatriates. This in turn means that local jobs will be taken over by expatriates especially because globalization has greatly facilitated movement of labour as a factor of production across national borders (Jordan, Brown & Russell, 2003).

2.1 Perspectives of Arab Students Generally

Generally, perceptions and career choice are not just limited to the students or the actual people making the real choices of careers. Instead, they extend to other people who have some influence over the career choosers. Whether it is parents, friends, peers, family, or community, influences by other in career choices have been known to extend far and wide in many countries across the world including the Middle East Countries and Jordan in particular (Guay, Senécal, Gauthier & Fernet, 2003). In Middle East, honour is highly regarded, therefore, having a career in a field that is not considered popular and/or honourable could be very detrimental to the career chooser's social standing (Al-Alak, 2006). This makes it even more likely that career choosers will consult widely before determining which careers to choose.

The aim of such consultations is not usually to get a helping hand regarding which careers are likely to match one's abilities as is the case in most Western states. Instead, the consultations are largely to determine which careers and career fields are more honourable and so worth taking. Dishonour is simply not permissible in many Middle Eastern societies (Jordan, Brown & Russell, 2003). Past evidence has shown that people have even had to be killed for simply choosing to engage in careers which are considered to be shameful or dishonourable to the families or communities of the career chooser (Jordan, Brown & Russell, 2003).

2.2 Perception of Jordan Students

There is greater concern for the integration of the needs of the labour markets and the requirements of universities' academic offerings generally. This is to compliment continues efforts by universities to impact

theoretical tendency in their approach to education to offer any job-specific skills to their students (Bin Tareef, 2009). While this is not all over the world, it is nonetheless a rampant practice and a trend that has specially affected developing countries like Jordan (Al-mushasha & Nassuora, 2012). For such nations, complaints regarding universities' theoretical and not practical approach to their academic offerings abound. The disconnection between academics and industry in terms of career development posed a great threat to manpower development in developing country like Jordan.

In Jordan, for instance, universities have been described as living in sort of 'ivory towers', locking themselves in too much theoretical content which in most cases is considered to be of little or no value to students especially in the labour market (Bin Tareef, 2009). In essence, the contents most of these universities offer their students are too theoretical to meet the aspirations and needs of the students at work place (Al-mushasha & Nassuora, 2012). In addition, Jordan, like other developing nations, greatly encourages foreign investment as a means of boosting the economy (Al-mushasha & Nassuora, 2012). This has made career planning to become unavoidable in the process of selecting university courses. This is in turn an indicator of management of quality assurance. The outcome of this has been higher education in the country has become very expensive, meaning that cost-effectiveness should be adhered to in every credit hour taken (Al-mushasha & Nassuora, 2012).

Due to sharp increase in demand for higher education, the country has continued to witness a rapid growth of institutions offering higher education degrees both public and private as ditto globally (Bin Tareef, 2009). While this trend is worth encouraging because it has ensured that most Jordanians seeking higher education are served, it has also produced quite negative results. Two notable negative outcome of this proliferation of institutions of higher learning in Jordan have been (1) compromising the quality of higher education and (2) increasing general unemployment (Bin Tareef, 2009). The proliferation in number of higher institutions is a threat to quality control management. No doubt, quality is sacrificed for quantity in a developing country like Jordan. Similarly, the limited scope of the country's economic growth results in breeding unemployed graduates turned out from these institutions that could not be absorbed into the labour market.

The challenges facing Jordan's higher education are not limited to increasing enrolment rates that are becoming unsustainable. Rather, other fundamental challenges existed along this common factor. The most prevailing issue is lack of sufficient skills imparted in the mostly young generation to help it compete effectively. Jordan's young population has increased tremendously in the recent past (Al-alak, 2006). However, the quality of education offered has not been able to fully equip the many young students graduating from higher education institutions to compete effectively on the labour market. This has made many to remain without jobs even though they are well educated and awarded university degrees (Al-alak, 2006). Therefore, Jordanians appeared limited by skills and competency right from school due non-integration of job skills alongside academics programs.

3.0 Literature Review

Career choice or development in private or public sector is determined by wide range of factors. While the working environment and other internal policies could influence the progression on the job, little consideration is given to external influences. Generally, both controllable and uncontrollable factors are taken into consideration when taking decisions of such nature. Factors within the control of decision maker such as pay package, working condition, length of service, hazards and risk involved, compensation, insurance, academic qualifications, gender and age can be influenced by job seeker. However, certain factors are beyond the control of job seeker, these include; management policy, leadership styles, cultural orientation, subjective norms, perceived behavioural control, weather, and community expectations.

In assessing the perception of Jordanian students, three main factors will be reviewed. These are family, community and cultural factors. The kind of work a family or community member does impacts the rest of the family and/or community. This is largely dependent on the nature of association between the individual, family and community concerned. The closer the associations the more the job will impact the second parties

(Leone & Chou, 1994; Teng et al., 1999; Kerka, 2000). The bottom-line is that choice of a career is very important and far from being an individual affair. Agreed, individual make the final and ultimate decision but many processes and people are involved in the process of career selection. Unfortunately, not many empirical studies have been undertaken to investigate the specific factors that actually contribute to or determine the choice of career in Jordanian context. The available empirical studies such as Al-alak (2006) have tended to concentrate so much on economic aspects. As a result, there has been a general shortage of studies on the cultural factors such as the role of family and community. This study tends to fill the literature gap by proposing the integration of some of the factors in Western world to Jordan context.

3.1 Family

In Jordan, it is known a fact that families and the community play a big role in their children's life decisions (Cheong & Chou, 1994; Teng, et al., 1999; Bin Tareef, 2009), and career choice could be one of them. Both the community and the family are especially important in the socialization of children. This is because every child in Jordan does not simply belong to the immediate family but to the whole community. Therefore, the community has a very big role to play (Cheong & Chou, 1994; Teng, et al., 1999; Bin Tareef, 2009). There has been nearly total agreement that families in Jordan play a key role in the career choices of their children (Taylor, Harris & Taylor, 2004). The role of family in career choice, therefore, is not an issue of contention as it is supported by empirical data and evidences. However, there seems to be no agreement regarding which specific family factors are most responsible for influencing career decisions.

However, in societies where males and females have very different upbringings and their roles are different (mostly in the Middle Eastern states), career choices differ markedly. Therefore, it was generally expected that males and females would want careers that are in line with the nature of their different type of socialization and general upbringing (Cenkseven-Onder, Kirdok&Isik, 2010). Similarly, Khasawneh (2010), in a study to investigate the factors influencing the career planning and development of university students in Jordan, discovered that there were five main determinants of career planning and development among Jordanian university students. These are parents, teachers, friends, high school academic experience, and self-efficacy.

Al-Rfou, (2013) conducted a study on the choice of business as a major from the perspective of business students at Tafila Technical University (TTU) in academic year 2011/2012. He found that parents play a very important role in the choice of majors for their children because they have a lot of influence over the major decisions these children make. According to Al-Rfou (2013), this influence is not just limited to parents. Instead, siblings and even friends do have significant influence over the decisions that these students made during their study. Such siblings and friends were important sources of influence on the majors that the participants took or studied (Al-Rfou, 2013). Thus, family influence encompasses the parents, siblings, neighbours, peer, teachers, acquaintance, role models, significant others and any other close ally of the children.

3.2 Community

In a study to investigate the factors influencing career choices of adolescents and young adults in rural Pennsylvania, Ferry (2006) found that family and community play a very important role in the career choices of young adults. Although none of the two was more prominent, the interrelatedness of the two was determined to be a major influencer of career choices. The general believe is that parents in rural areas are more likely to influence their children's careers choices as indeed they do influence many other decisions in the children's lives (Guay, Senécal, Gauthier & Fernet, 2003). Interestingly, Ferry (2006) concluded that young adults tend to learn about and explore careers (which they end up choosing) through their interaction in the context of family, school, and community. Notable factors within these major ones were the economic and social circumstances of the families and/or communities concerned (Ferry, 2006; Guay, Senécal, Gauthier &Fernet, 2003).

Generally, the young people drawn from communities that were more affluent tended to consider wider career ranges before settling on one (Ferry, 2006). This was because they had more school and family support in the career exploration endeavours. It was established that parents were the leading sources of valuable learning experiences for the young people by way of their role modelling and supporting activities that were assistive in

career exploration (Ferry, 2006). Constantine, Wallace and Kindaichi (2005) examined the various contextual factors in the career decision status of African American adolescents. More specifically, they undertook an examination of the extent to which perceived occupational barriers and perceived parental support predicted career certainty and career indecision in the selected sample of African American adolescents. According to them, perceived occupational barriers positively predicted career indecisions. This means that adolescents were less likely to make careers decisions in circumstances where occupational barriers were perceived (Constantine, et al., 2005). Constantine, Wallace and Kindaichi (2005) study also revealed that contextual factors play a very significant role in the determination of the careers that African American adolescents choose. Support from families and even close relatives was found to be an important influencer of the careers one takes up. Actually, the study revealed that in the absence of parental and family support in career decision-making, the adolescents concerned could end up being negatively affected. This in turn could hamper their educational and career aspirations (Constantine, et al., 2005).

In a related study, Hairston (2000) investigated the manner in which parents influence African American students' decisions to prepare for vocational teaching careers. This study supports the findings by Constantine, et al. (2005) that contextual factors, including parental support, play a very important role in the choice of careers for African American adolescents. On her part, Hairstone (2000) used quantitative methodology to achieve her research objectives. Interviews were conducted on 12 African American college students to ascertain the manner in which their parents influenced their preparation for vocational teaching careers and specific teaching specialties. His findings revealed the following five factors according to Hairston (2000): (a) desire to imitate parents' altruistic behaviour and role as community contributors; (b) high academic and career expectations by parents; (c) parental support for academic and occupational endeavours; (d) parents providing early exposure to vocational subject matter and/or the teaching field, and (e) parents aiding in the discovery of aptitudes and interests in vocational subject matter. Conclusion can be drawn from the foregoing that the environment (including people) where children grown up greatly mode their decision when they become adult. Such decisions include career choice and other future endeavours.

3.3 Cultural Factors

People of different cultures have also been found to prefer certain careers over others. This indicate that there are certain culture-specific factors that in one way or the other affect the career choices of these people. For instance, Mashall et al. (2011) argued that it is very common for children drawn from communities of First Nations people to end up in careers that their parents or other members of the community had or still have. This has been found to be because children born in such communities often have no access to the outside world and all they hear and see is what their fellow community members do (Mashall et al., 2011). Juntunen et al. (2001) argued that people from the First Nations are often quite opposed to modernity and would prefer that their traditional ways of life are maintained at all costs. This way of thinking no doubt gets passed on to their siblings who either end up doing what their fathers, mothers, siblings, or community members did; or to take up careers that have a close semblance to the careers that were common or acceptable in their community (Juntunen et al., 2001).

Take for instance, a community where parents love serving in the local church or mosque, their children will also grow up with a general liking for community work (Draper & Louw, 2007). This is the same influence that occurs when it comes to career choice. Since children look up to their parents or older siblings for guidance in life, these children often take everything associated with or done by their parents or older siblings as good. Therefore, children whose parents or older siblings are teachers always grow up adoring teachers. If the parents are or were physicians, then the children grow up with good perceptions about physicians. As a result of this heavy inclination towards the careers of their parents or older siblings, children tend to end up in the same careers (Draper & Louw, 2007). However, most children tend to unconsciously take up careers which were held by their parents simply because they happened to be born to those parents. This behaviour has been found to be especially common in cases where such children lack exposure to other people who could influence them otherwise (Draper & Louw, 2007).

In a related manner, there are higher chances that children raised by rural parents are more likely to take up careers that are the same as, or similar to, those of their parents or older siblings than children raised in urban areas. The reason is that unlike in urban areas where children get more exposure to different people and career options, rural areas offer little exposure to children who are exclusively raised there (Draper & Louw, 2007). However, this proposition failed to address some critical aspects. A notable oversight in the argument is that it does not appreciate the role of compulsive or coercive force in career choices made in this manner. Many children have ended up in careers of their parents largely because these parents, while not necessarily forcing the children to take up the career, they have made all other career options unavailable or impossible for the children. Therefore, this ought not to be described as influence *per se* but as lack of options. In essence, a career is chosen not because it is the one the chooser really wants but because it is the only one available. Truly speaking, there can be no 'choice' when there is only one option.

In a study to investigate the relative influence of career-choice factors on accounting students from different cultural backgrounds, Auyeung and Sands (1997) found out that the choice of accounting as a career was affected by different factors that were different across cultures. That is, accountant students from different cultures showed that they had chosen accounting as a career based on quite different motivational or causal factors. Using the individualism- collectivism dichotomy, the study specifically examined the importance of factors which influence the comparative career choices of Australian, Hong Kong and Taiwanese students in selecting accountancy as a career. It was found that for Hong Kong and Taiwanese students, the factors that had the greatest impact on career choice included parental influence, peer influence, teacher influence and association with others in the field (Auyeung & Sands, 1997). On the part of Australian students, however, the major influencing factors were aptitude for subject matter (Auyeung & Sands, 1997). It was further found that material entity factors such as availability of employment, prestige and social status, earning potential, cost of education and year of study emerged as formative concerns for Hong Kong and Taiwanese students, more so than for their Australian counterparts (Auyeung & Sands, 1997).

Finally, the Australian students could have been more assured of jobs than their Chinese counterparts. This is because finding a job (in whatever career) in Australia is more certain than in China (due to the former having higher employment chances). For the Chinese, therefore, a career has to be weighed in terms of its earning potential before a decision is made with regard to whether or not to choose it. To this end, careers that promise higher earning potential are more likely to be chosen by students from the Chinese culture than those from Australia. From the study, it can be concluded that different cultures emphasize different aspects in their life; and these aspects are therefore considered whenever critical life-altering decisions are being considered or made. Therefore, the ultimate career chosen is a reflection of the core values of the culture of the individuals concerned. Other than the East-West divide, there is also the issue of socialism and multiculturalism. While Australia is a multicultural country, China (including Hong Kong and Taiwan) is a purely monoculture one. Thus, cultural influences played vital role in decision making of any group irrespective of either developed or developing society. Culture embraces all aspects of life.

4.0 Conceptual Framework

Extent theories have revealed interlink between proposed constructs and career choice in different settings (Wiseman, 2010; Kulkami, 2012; Kunnen, 2013). However, cultural differences have been extensively argued to influence both teenage and adolescent decision (Bin Tareef, 2009; Ferry, 2006; Crossley & Mubarik, 2002). This study reviewed literatures across countries before conceptualizing the model according to theory. Therefore, family, community and culture have been proposed in this study to influence career choice of a typical Jordanian student.

Fig. 1 Schematic illustration of the relationships

5.0 Conclusion

The conclusion recapitalized the variables proposed by giving in-depth definition for better understanding thus: family is defined as household, or all those who live in one house (eg parents, children, and servants); parents and the their children; the children alone; the descendants of one common ancestry; race; honorable or noble descent; a group of people related to one another, or otherwise connected; etc. The level of intimacy within and among family member greatly influences their decision including career choice. Similarly, community is defined as a body of people in the same locality; the public in general, people having common rights, a body of people leading a common life or under socialistic or similar organizations; a group of people who have common interests, characteristics or culture. Teenagers that grown up within a community may likely be influence by the general norm of the community when making decision including career choice. Lastly, culture is defined as the perceptions, beliefs and standards which people acquire from the society in which they grew up. Differences in cultural values both between countries and between ethnic groups within country (subcultures) are often important in designing segmentation strategies for products or services introduced into market. Culture is simply the norms and shared attitudes that pervade in a society. It may be expressed in symbols, rituals and the language used by society members. It thus constitutes the distinctive characteristics of a typical society.

Career choice being a multidisciplinary issue, appears to be given a lot of attention; and as much as possible efforts have been made to determine or predict the factors that influence or contribute to career decision-making. This has been done largely to ensure that the whole process of career choice is facilitated as much as possible given that it is one of the most important decisions in any person's life. However, the one important aspect that is poorly covered in the literature or is entirely lacking is the analysis of specific cultural and family factors in the context of a specific non-Western country. Most studies conducted have actually been done in the West. Therefore, the current study is an attempt to filling this literary gap by focusing on a combination of specific family, community, and cultural factors in the context of a Middle Eastern Arab country: Jordan. The study is a review work aimed at proposing integration of factors used in previous studies in advanced countries, however, specific factors will be consider for Jordan when items are develop for empirical studies.

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